

Author Correction: A high-density and high-confinement tokamak plasma regime for fusion energy

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07545-3>

Published online: 22 May 2024

Correction to: *Nature* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07313-3>

Published online 24 April 2024

Open access

 Check for updates

S. Ding, A. M. Garfalo, H. Q. Wang, D. B. Weisberg, Z. Y. Li, X. Jian, D. Eldon, B. S. Victor, A. Marinoni, Q. M. Hu, I. S. Carvalho, T. Odstrčil, L. Wang, A. W. Hyatt, T. H. Osborne, X. Z. Gong, J. P. Qian, J. Huang, J. McClenaghan, C. T. Holcomb & J. M. Hanson

In the version of the article initially published, the first affiliation of A. Marinoni (University of California San Diego, La Jolla, CA, USA) was missing and has now been added to the HTML and PDF versions of the article.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

© The Author(s) 2024